
Impact of Non-Academic Stress on Perceived Employability of Management Professional students

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Abstract

Over-stress among students can become a reason that can cause serious issues and make bad impact on students. Student life is the most interesting life of an individual. New friends, new place, new challenges make impact life and can also make it stressful. Stress management include technique to prepare an individual to deal how to cope with mental stress. Techniques of stress management include resolution of conflicts, self-management, positive attitude, self-talking, breathing, exercise, meditation, resting and dieting. Present generation is facing lot of pressure in learning more and more in comparison to past generation. It can also be stressful in handling a heavy as well as challenging workload, many students also experience stress because of everyday academic activities. However, overstress may also be the reason making serious impact on students. Student life is the most exciting time in one's life.

Management education required to be holistic, targeted, and personalized with the goal to remove the gaps existing between requirement of industry and curriculum of academic that focus on attitude, corporate awareness, grooming and development of managerial skills. Interaction with Industry needs to be strengthen by inviting senior people from industry delivering lecture to ensure students to get linked with live projects of industry. Learning must be student centric that would result in development on all areas like lateral thinking, analytical reasoning, and solving case studies

Keywords: Non-Academic, Stress, Employability, Students, Management, Education

Introduction

The efficacy of management education can be enhanced by shifting the focus from tradition system of learning to development of skills and carefully working with the industry for catering that increases the complications and constantly changing requirement of industry. Applicants who seek career prospects in the field of management are observed because of many questions in their mind regarding success in their field. MBA is a professional course has become a choice of many students these days. This course not just develops the skills of management but it also makes students confident to take important decisions in their field. This brilliant professional program creates entrepreneurial attitude. This program helps in the development of entrepreneurial attitude. The management education conveys skills to students of management college who are facing rigorous challenges. This management program helps in the development of leadership qualities in students to get people done things by others in efficient manner. Businesses in present time need professionals and competitive skills for surviving in this era of competitive environment. In order to capture the share in market, grow with customer data base, touching new heights of success in management education, which is considered as a strong tool. An individual who are equipped with managerial and technical skills might set up their own business and can also provide employment. Usually, an individual must be equipped with good capability mapping. The huge corporate is demanding for managerial talents for benefits of global opportunities of marketing. All elements of management education like curriculum, course and teaching pedagogy, interface of industry and institutions, development of faculty, consultancy, placements, and research projects making contribution in development of employment skills of management students. The modern system of

management education requires changes for improvement in employability for job seekers. Redesigning of curriculum, management institutions must utilize ICT for the process of teaching and learning, improving research quality and for development of faculties in order to meet the shortage of tutors. With the assistance of live projects, and case studies the employability skills of management students can be improved, it can also be done with the help of group discussions, market survey and simulation of exercises that would also help in making them more competent in global scenario (Singhal & Saini, 2020).

However, a business school is not just a place where only education is provided, instead it is a place where leaders at world level are created and promoted with the long-term vision, integrity and honesty.

Creation of knowledge and its circulation must be the main purpose of business schools. As management education is sector based and there is a continuous change that result in the need of distinct management skills and knowledge at different time, it is suggested to evaluate academic syllabus and, in its designing, to match with the demand of market. Faculty must be motivated and engaged in research work as well as counselling that would lead to creation of knowledge and inventions. To improve the mental and physical health of students, it is the responsibility of parents as well as teachers to encourage students actively in academic performance. The prime result of these activities would be improvement in academic performance as well as improve their memory. There will also be decrease in the rate of suicides, health issues and mental illness among students. In the academic life of students, stress has become normal and have become the reason of internal as well as external expectation of parents and teachers. Students are highly exposed to issues related with academic stress as transitions appear at an individual as well as social level. It thus, becomes imperious to acknowledge the source as well as influence of academic stress to originate proper and effective strategies of intervention. Quantitative design of research is used where students were tested by using like management, commerce, basic science, and humanities. Personal inadequacy, failure, inter-personal difficulties with tutors are common dimensions that needs to be analysed along with gender differences. Understanding the stress source facilitates the growth and expansion of effective counselling module and strategies of intervention by counsellors to assist students reduce stress (Reddy, Menon & Thattil, 2018). In another study, it is observed that there are some stressors as well like too many assignments allotted to students, competition with peers, poor and failures related with other students or teachers. Academic stressors also include perception of students towards extensive base of knowledge needed by them and their perception regarding shortage of time for its development (Prabu, 2015). Physical, mental and emotional health of students along with their academic performance are impacted significantly by academic stress that might can reach to high level. Stress assessment is important to avoid bad situations. The stress level of students is evaluated frequently through psychological methods like self-report questionnaire and interviews. Hussein (2024) Organization today's look for additional qualities beyond academic qualification from the increasing number of management graduates. In this regard, soft skills have gaining lot of prominence in the modern workforce facilitating them with the achievement at the workplace and are considered as vital element of academic as well as professional victory. Soft skills are the collection of attitudes, habits, character traits, and manners that make contribution to capability to work well with other people as well as become a productive employee. There are two categories into which skills can be divided – hard skills and soft skills. Hard skills are required for particular type of job like technical tasks. Soft skills are needed for effective communication at the workplace. Training sessions must be conducted to assist students make improvement in self-marketing capabilities like skills and concepts of marketing. Students must be taught how creation of a network for gathering information regarding the desired position of job or job opportunity offered by the organization. To help students manage their anger in effective manner, training programs must be organized that would help them in controlling anger, emotion and behaviour.

There are many other risk factors related with anxiety, stress and depression among students that also include academic, mental, social, biological, and financial factors. Identification of such factors at the early stage can assist in providing mental support and prevent them from these factors getting at high level. No significant difference was found between academic stress of students from self-financed or government school or students from rural or urban schools. The main reasons of academic stress were divided into seven categories like tests and examinations, stress from teachers and parents, peer pressure, expectation and pressure from parents, social elements, infrastructure, management of time, and self-inflicted elements.

Mandal (2021) Stress is common in modern life. It has become a part of everyday academic life of a student because of many reasons and expectations of themselves as well as their parent's. Achievements related to academic life, and its goals sometime causes lot of stress. Academic stress can be considered essential element for variation in academic goal achievement. Excess stress level can lead to mental issues like anxiety and depression. It has become a wide spreading challenge across all countries. The main factors of stress are highlighted in this part of the study that make adverse impact on the academic life of student. It is understood here that expectations of parents, competition, grades, tuitions, vast curriculum, examination and failures, missed lectures, high level of workload are some of the other common factors of stress among students. There is close association between academic stress and the attainment of academic achievement. The first step to live a stress-free life is to quit over-analysis.

This work can assist in identifying the main cause and assisting students to identify solutions to this problem and would assist in enjoying the school life without stress.

Literature Review

Better academic performance and high self-perceived employability are strongly associated with each other where student with good academic performance feels surer about his or her career prospects.

Student's perception about employability is positively influenced by the institutions that offers "comprehensive career services, networking opportunities and targeted support" to their students. As compared to students that lack relevant qualification and work experience, employer usually prefer the candidate that has these qualities. The students view themselves more employable when they get some work experience before they begin their higher education. This will help them to get more confidence in finding their job after studies as compared to others. There are students that study engineering and get some work experience by joining internship programs in some corporate offices to gain experience and make them more employable. This approach makes them more confident in the perceived employability as compared to others that skip this step and step down directly in job market.

Kovacs & Zarandne (2022) stated that requirement of jobs in digital marketing for graduates and junior employability skills are studied for occupations like social media managers, digital marketing managers, and assistant digital marketing managers. The employability skills are changing swiftly with the advancing technologies and digitalization of global progress of supply chain and global economies are integrating.

Industry 4.0 and economies are interrelated at many interfaces that lead to a growing research body in many aspects like sustainability, motivation, and HRM. One of the key issues for higher education is employability of a graduate, the improvement of students from universities and to make them ready for the workplace is highly difficult in the field of digital marketing. For management graduates, the non-academic stressors include social isolation, financial pressure, expectations of family, and difficulties in balancing social, personal and academic life. All such factors combined with academic pressure such as tests, examinations, workload make contribution to considerable stress level among management professional students. It is has become crucial to address these non-academic factors to improve well-

being of students along with the academic performance. Some strategies to deal with such challenges is to provide students with some financial assistance, mental health services and social support. There are many academic as well as non-academic elements that have potential relation with emotional suffering as well. Different stressors like improper relations between students and teachers, learning distress, concerns related to future, poor mental health, etc make poor impact on students. Other probable stressors that make poor impact on the mental health of students are academic pressure, financial condition, relationship with parents, parental pressure, physical illness, and emotional problems.

Awang et al. (2021) Studies shows that non-academic responsibilities make minimal impact on students. Therefore, other factors are not within the scope to study but might make contribution on the job-related stress. It is observed that Academicians play important role in the life of students. Universities are facing lot of serious issues and challenges due to competitive pressure from other universities, it is coupled with the requirements to meet the demand of stakeholders towards the excellence of university, the job of academician is to expand not just academics but also non-academic responsibilities. Academicians who are overloaded with academic as well as non-academic responsibilities might face stress related to jobs that might lead to poor quality of job making negative impact on the image of university.

Shesharao (2024) study examines the modern environment of work, featured with rising demand for productivity and attrition of work and life boundaries has worsened the challenges of management of family responsibilities. Such pressure has been shown to make a negative influence on family life that led to anxious relations and low quality of family time. The workforce of modern nation is shaped by the complicated communication between work and family responsibilities that creates potential stress for employed as well as unemployed candidates. To understand the broader occupational stress such communication is critical for stress issues and conflicts between work and family. Both groups can experience different type of stress the source, nature and results of their stress might be different significantly on the basis of status of employment, societal norms, and personal situations. The relation between work and family conflicts is explored by this work, it also explored occupational stress, and status of employment of an individual, it has provided a complete overview of theoretical framework and empirical findings as well.

Choi (2024) study states that Empathetic supervisors who accommodate family responsibilities of employees set a tone of understanding and flexibility permeating the workplace. Support of supervisor is manifested in different ways like providing flexibility in schedule of work, understanding the requirement for time off, and offers resources or advice to manage conflicts between work and family. Such support does not just help in alleviating work and family conflicts, but it also strengthens the perception that company value and support well-being of employees. To enhance practical actions further, companies can implement flexible arrangement of work like flexi-time and option of telecommunication where ever possible helping employees in management of their work and family responsibilities. Career development program offered by company along with opportunities for advancement can develop loyalty of employees and reduction in turnover.

Kumar & Srivastava (2023) study states that Severe stress can be easily resolved whereas chronic stress stays for weeks or month that can cause many different health issues. Chronic stress might lead to increasing heart rate, increase blood pressure, muscle tension, high consumption of oxygen, stress hormones, increase the glucose in the blood, etc. Stress and distress are usually used interchangeably. Stress level varies from individual-to-individual regardless anxiety and depression can be caused because of high level of stress or extreme level of stress disrupting the mental as well as physical health of an individual. Various section of society can be affected by stress in different ways. The most exposed section of society can get affected easily like youth or old age people. Many mental, physical as well as behavioral reactions can get risen due to stress that can eventually lead to health issues. Employers

are suggested to dismiss stress that are faced by employees, as it is essential for them to seek stress management methods actively. There are multitude of factors within the settings of organization having the potential of making contribution to stress experience. Virtually every side of employment has the potential to work as a stress encouraging element for an individual. There are various elements in the work environment can make significant influence on the stress that is experienced by an individual. The agreement among specialists expected more measures to help employees deal with the overseeing stress level and work pressure. The proposal combined the expansion of health programs, the assistance of pressure the board course, and the teaching of staff for achieving the balance serious with fun activities.

Wright, Walker & Hall (2023) study concluded that as workplace and perceived stressors of life might influence a feeling of burnout and mental health directly, burnout so not found to be appearing to show a strong impact on the perception of mental well-being of an individual. It can be proved worth considering if the burnout might be considered another type of mental health issue rather as a direct contributor as a coach of mental health. However, emotional exhaustion has not reflected as a strong relation, disconnection did not show any considerable relation with mental health results, depression, or well-being.

Tunda & Bhuyan (2025) examined that a big impact is made by homesickness on how a student is involved in their social life and studies. High level of homesick of a students get them away from social life and other social activities, and make them stay away from events organized in events that also make them feel lonely. Academic behavior is felt by students that they struggle with missing classes, procrastination, and less participation in group discussion that ultimately led to poor grades in class.

Staying in contact with family members, academic activities, and counselling services are some of the strategies to deal with homesickness. Support programs must be organized by college that can include good quality of mental health resources, peer monitoring, and other social events that can connect and settle students in different city or town. In order to help students actively to deal with homesickness through such support systems, the college must develop a friendly climate that can support students mainly from first year to get adjusted in the environment, to succeed academically, and to build up their strength. The study highlights the strategic emotional as well as academic support for student's success who would have probably been going through homesickness triggering their success and helping them to give good academic performance.

Padaganur et al. (2025) study revealed by the findings that there are consequences of homesickness for expatriates as well as for the organization. These consequences include mental and social disorders, worsening of physical health that can make damaging impact on well-being of an individual, work results and commitments of organization. A significant negative personal as well as organizational consequences can be resulted from homesickness when there is no systematic intervention of HRM is available, along with institutional framework for supporting expatriates with diverse requirements. This is related with the inadequacy of preparations of expatriates before departing from home, the lack of in-assignment support. Other approaches also showed a level of success in some of the cases. For example, dependency and dis-connection with work as more efforts are used to deal with homesickness as contrasting to concentrate on the role of expatriate. The challenges of emigrants in developing nation can be paused due to homesickness as it is a common experience among students living in hostels or who have moved out of their home to pursue higher education. It is a feeling of desire for comfort, family surroundings and routine that students were having when they were at home. Homesickness is an emotional and mental distress that any student face and it make an adverse impact on the mental and physical health as well as their academic performance. Changed environment can be considered as the main reason of homesickness. It is nearly a universal experience that make significant impact on students mainly who live away and far from their home for the first time. This challenge can make bad impact on

the mental health, difficult to get adjusted in social environment and academic performance also gets impacted in poor way. It is found in many studies that students of young age face high level of homesickness due to many factors that can be occupation of their parents, religion, etc. To address homesickness by coping strategies, emotional support, and intervention of institutions is highly required for enhancement of overall adjustment of students and for the success in journey of education.

Ghatol & Bharucha (2024) study examined the link of stress with other elements like frustration and depression are expanded. Stress can be considered as any factor that acts internally and externally making adaptation to environment hard inducing high level effort on the part of an individual for maintaining a level of evenness between male and female as well as environment. Therefore, elements causing a substantial stress among students are poor management of time, poor skills of study, overload of homework, difficulty of meeting expectations of teachers and parents, travelling to schools, poor relations with teachers, fear of failure, tm bad skill of communication, peer pressure, etc.

Kaur et al. (2024) study examined that no difference is found in the average perception of stress based on gender, but pressure of studies, income of family, peer and parental pressure appears as stress and considered as contributing element. Pressure of time, curriculum, examinations are found to be highly significant elements that affect the perception towards stress. Students at young age are facing high level of stress making harmful impact on mental and physical health, poor self-respect, low level of optimism, lacking self-efficacy. This work also analyses the elements affecting perceived stress level among students in HEI. Various other factors are also examined that make influence on perceived stress among students. Identification of more substantial elements augmenting perceived stress among students is essential for supporting and assisting proper policies and guidelines for transformation in educational system and improving overall health. It is mentioned by students that involvement of social media is a relief factor. All such elements make potential of leading mental sickness that include sadness and feeling of facing failure and sadness. It also led to matters like disturbance in sleeping pattern, increase in blood pressure, gaining or losing weight, etc.

Mishra & Choudhari (2024) in his study stated that Stress is a big word and can make big influence, but can be dealt with little changes that we bring in everyday life. Stress can be experienced by anyone like politicians, housewives, government officials, financiers, managers, and many others, but it is high among students. Stress is considered as a subjective process and include personal analysis of an individual and pledge to a threatening event. With regards to students, academic stress has become a main part of competitive life. Over-burden syllabus, its elevation, environment of school, relationship with faculty, peer pressure, competition, choice for future career and many other elements start influencing young students and they get stressed unknowingly. Anxiety and stress among young students are as common and dominant like adults. Carelessness of parents, high level of expectations and high performance, mistreated children, tension of growing up, demands and responsibility are some of the common reasons of stress among students.

Research Methodology:

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

The Problem undertaken by investigator is stated as “To know the Impact of Non Academic Stress on Perceived Employability of Management Professional students.”

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

The investigator of the present study framed the following objective:

- To find out the differences among respondents on basis of Gender.
- To find out the level of Academic Stress on Perceived Employability of Management Professional Students in Chitrakoot district, India.”

METHODOLOGY:

Study survey was conducted among 30 management professional students to know the Impact of Non-Academic Stress on Perceived Employability. "Random sampling method" were used to collect and analyse the data.

DESCRIPTION OF SCALE:

In the present study the scale consists of 24 items: **Personal Stress** Item 1 to 5, **Family Stress** Item 6 to 10, **Social & Peer Stress** Item 11 to 15, **Intrapersonal challenges** Item 16 to 20, **Future Concerns** item 21 to 24 and each item have five alternate responses i.e. "SA (Strongly Agree)", "A (Agree)", "UD (Un Decided)", "D (Decided)", "SD (Strongly Disagree)". So, the scoring to the response given by student should be like the following:

RESPONSE	CODE
SA	5
A	4
UD	3
D	2
SD	1

Data Analysis

In the total population of study survey males are 73.33% and females are 26.67%.

Conclusion

Management education is the education of business. This area of education develops the required knowledge, skills, and attitude for handling the industry, commerce and trading. Business studies and commerce are the art to perform that need professional skills and inculcation. However, every art or skill requires some type of scientific knowledge as a primary foundation. Obtaining theoretical knowledge sharpens the mind and intellect of a students. Thus, business education and commerce studies should provide a student full knowledge and understanding of theory that they would apply practically and from their experience. More stress is given on trainings in the applied business sciences that has become an important part of social responsibility of a business. Business studies and commerce education needs to be oriented to practical micro as well as macro situations. Easiest explanation for a student is lacking knowledge with regards to skills associated with the jobs in project management. It is expected from students to have good understanding of skills and knowledge required to be a project professional, and have the capability of connecting with past working experience with skill development that would make contribution towards employability. However, acquisitions of skills require some basic foundations. Theoretical knowledge assists to improve faculties that enables an individual to think with freedom and independently. Training and new skills are required for dealing with such challenges. Technological advancement should be included in basic syllabus of business education. Management education is important for the growth of Indian economy. Employability skills that are being recognized as a constructive approach helping them to meet challenges of the modern workplace. Many studies have indicated that there is lack of market-driven employability skills among graduates, these skills are highly required for the success at the workplace in 21st century. Employability skills include responsibility, personality, honesty, dedication, adaptability, sociability, initiative, ambition, creativity, they must be ready to face everyday challenges, and must be visionary thinkers. It is also observed that employability skills can also be different from industry to industry like, manufacturing sector prefer sociability and honesty, financial sectors usually prefer responsibility, honesty, and adaptability, engineering sector like more of a creativity. This work also discusses historical overview and different perspective defining employability skills. This work would be proved useful for present students, academic institutes, potential employers along with stakeholders and policy-makers.

It is suggested that developing a scale of employability on the basis of expectations of employers can serve as a valuable tool to identify and address the mismatch between expectations of employers and possessed skills of graduates. Many different factors like behaviour, individual and environmental variables make significant impact on perceived employability on students. Besides, some past studies have deviated on specific elements like partial components of personality traits, demographics, career engagement, political skills, and labour market condition. It authenticates the significance of “Career Construction Theory” to interpret the perceived employability among students and enhances the understanding of researchers about how perceived employability has progressed. It is observed that students who have high level of psychological capital show high level of confidence, resilience, optimism, and hope when tackle challenges of career correlating with high level of perceived employability and satisfaction with career. The stress of family responsibility among management graduates analyses the influence of balancing demands of academics with family obligations, possibly leads to conflicts between work and family, stress, and its influence on mental as well as physical health. The relationship between children and their parents is dependent on attitude, understanding and perspective. Positive views of parents, the association between them and children will be better considerably when they have a negative attitude. Response to unpleasant emotion by parents have variety ways that can be classified as supportive and non-supportive.

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